

The Alan Turing Institute

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Can machine learning be used to identify code vulnerabilities?

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Software security is granted by the absence of bugs and weaknesses in code. As software becomes increasingly complex, often consisting of millions of lines of code, checking the code for errors becomes very costly. Despite existing static analysis tools, a high false-positive rate means this has a large manual overhead, since it is difficult to demonstrate the absence of a bug in code.

This project investigated how to use machine learning algorithms to improve on existing automated vulnerability discovery tools. This could be used to inform the development of new tools to be used alongside existing static analysis methods and formal verification where appropriate.

1.2 Data overview

The principal dataset we used was the standardized test suite Juliet, which provides a collection of 64,099 test cases in the C/C++ language. Each example demonstrates a specific type of code weakness that falls under a unique category (e.g. stack-based buffer overflow, which is labelled CWE121).

Other datasets are available as part of NIST's SARD (the Software Assurance Reference Dataset), which aims to provide researchers with a catalogue of known security flaws in a variety of settings.

1.3 Main objectives

There were two overall objectives to this project:

1. Exploring how to train a machine learning system to identify weaknesses in code, improving the sensitivity of traditional static analysis tools, prioritized by confidence level, in order to guide further analysis of the code.

2. Building a database of real-world bugs, using a commit history to identify the introduction and fixes of particular bugs, categorized by the type of weakness.

1.4 Approach

1.4.1 Task 1 - identifying weaknesses

Identifying weaknesses in code can result either in 1- classifying a given code as being bug-free or not, or 2- locating the exact lines where a bug appears. The latter approach, involving model structure inference, is more difficult and would have required an in-depth analysis exceeding our resources. Instead, we concentrated our efforts on implementing the former, which is also a challenging task, as programs consist of large code bases, where in the worst scenario every section interacts with every other section.

After a necessary pre-processing step, and given the complexity of this task, we had to reduce the dimensionality by extracting relevant features. Then, we considered the suitability of different ML algorithms for this classification, and selected the best methods we could implement given our resources.

Data representation

The first difficulty was to find an adequate representation of the data, as this field of research is still in his infancy. We explored a number of representations of programs that could be used as model input. The unit of analysis we chose was the function level. We opted for two representations fit for classification:

1. Abstract Syntax Trees (ASTs): a straightforward tree-based representation of the code, preserving its syntactical structure
2. Intermediate Representation (IR): a semantical approach consisting of sequence of tokens generated from a low-level representation of the code close to assembly.

They shared the advantage of being the result of running the preprocessor on the source file, providing a fast and reliable implementation. Ideally, code analysis would benefit from designing a novel mixed approach, both syntactic and semantic.

Data preprocessing

While the given dataset contained labelled data, its structure was not straightforwardly fit for classification tasks. Some files included several alternative corrections for a single defective function, others involved multiple functions for a single fix, and in some cases the corrections were spanned over multiple files. Consequently, extracting well-structured labelled samples required a first stage of familiarization and experimentation with the data. Because of the time constraint, we eventually targeted a subsample of the dataset, but with more resources this pre-processing step could be extended to incorporate the disparate file structures.

Machine Learning algorithms

After building two baseline models for comparative purposes, one based on static analysis and the other providing a zero-order model, we identified two different ML approaches that seemed promising to solve this problem: Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Tree-Structured Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) corresponding to two different representations of the data.

RNNs provide a natural framework for modelling sequential data and are therefore well-suited for use with the IR representation. For feature extraction, we tried two approaches to tokenize the data:

1. One-hot encoding, the most straightforward technique where the vector is the same size as the number of words in the dataset
2. Word-embedding, reducing the vector size by training a skip-gram model to predict words neighbourhood.

Both were tested with Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs), a specific RNN architecture adapted to process long-term structure, to

classify functions as either correct (without a weakness) or incorrect (containing a specified weakness).

CRFs, another kind of sequential classifiers, are notably fit for structured prediction. Thus, they allow a classification targeted at individual syntactic nodes of the AST representation, trained to distinguish correct from incorrect nodes while learning from their location and interconnectedness. This implementation required a meticulous fine-tuning of the features, considered in section Tree-structured conditional random fields.

1.4.2 Task 2 - building a database of real-world examples

The methods we used were only applied to a clean dataset, intentionally designed for this kind of experiments. Applying them to unpolished source code will first require testing and adjusting them over a database of real-world examples, potentially providing a far richer context for feature extraction. The solution we considered was web scraping from Github. Selecting relevant data and labelling them correctly is a complex task, deserving a careful examination. In section 5 we explain the design challenges involved in such an enterprise and describe a procedure which, given adequate manpower, could be implemented in order to extend the existing dataset.

1.5 Main Conclusions

Machine learning algorithms can provide at least two kinds of solutions to detect vulnerabilities in code, either by predicting errors or by inferring their location. Machine learning could also help build an improved representation of the data, which current state is not fit to the high dimensionality involved by this problem.

Using existing representations and straightforward applications, we trained a Recurrent Neural Network on the classification task and achieved an accuracy of 81% on the test set, an improvement compared to the baseline of random guessing at 72% showing that the approach is promising.

We have provided several ideas that could be used as jumping-off points for further exploration.

1.6 Limitations

This problem is a novel field, with little literature on the topic, and it demands a specific combination of skills. Consequently, our contribution was mainly exploratory.

Technically, due to the constraints of the challenge, we decided to focus our effort on just one type of weakness, namely CWE 121, stack-based buffer overflow.

Finally, the dataset we used contained only synthetic code examples, leaving open the question of the extent to which the current results are transferable to real-world code code.

1.7 Recommendations and further work

- Exploring alternatives for source code representation.
- Research on feature engineering in the context of the particular problem of detecting vulnerabilities in code.
- Creating a real-world dataset and testing on real-world data.
- Additional ML approaches (e.g., tree and graph CNNs, tree-structured LSTM RNN [9]).
- Testing our models on other types of problems (CWE numbers) in Juliet.
- Training a machine to learning the domain of abstract interpretations.

2 Quantitative problem formulation

2.1 Source code representation

At least two problems could be tackled using machine learning techniques to identify vulnerabilities in code:

1. Classification problem: given an input, does it belong to the class good or bad?
2. Location identification problem: given an input, where is the anomaly?

In the dataset, code samples are labelled as good or bad, making them a priori good candidates for binary classification. However, before running a standard classifier on the data, one must make sure that the cause of the vulnerability is meaningfully expressed in the data fed to the algorithm. Within the working dataset, and using existing representations, this information remains ambiguous in some instances (explained in more details in section Problem-Solution Database). Therefore, designing an adequate representation of the data (section Data overview and data representation), and selecting relevant features (section Machine Learning Approaches) were both necessary for classification.

3 Data overview and data representations

3.1 Dataset description

We used the Juliet Test Suite [nst-srd-test], which provides examples of C/C++ code. The examples are organised under CWE numbers [cwe-c], a classification system for common software weakness types. For each weakness type, the dataset provides samples of vulnerable code, along with one to several corresponding corrected samples. Each sample can span over multiple lines, functions or files.

3.2 Data quality issues

There were some systematic structural differences between the safe and vulnerable code examples, mainly due to having multiple strategies for correcting a single bug, that had to be removed with a pre-processing step. Furthermore, when tokenizing, many safe examples contained a similar small set of tokens containing the string "good". The main concern was that something like 'good', which was the name of each of the bug-free functions, would be a unique token, and would only appear in the bug-free cases, allowing the algorithm to "cheat" by just looking for this token.

3.3 Data representation

There are many possible program representations, ranging from raw source code, which includes idiosyncrasies of the programmer such as variable names, comments and coding style in general, to machine code which will have lost all this information and in addition will be specific to the platform it was compiled on. The best representation can fall somewhere in between these two extremes depending on the targeted machine learning algorithm.

Our implementations were based on two specific representations provided with Clang, a compiler front-end for C: Abstract Syntax Trees (ASTs) and Intermediate Representation (IR).

Let us illustrate the representations of source code as an AST or an IR with a simple example. We use 'CWE476_NULL_Pointer_Dereference__binary_if_01.c' for simplicity, rather than the bug that we focus on in data analysis. The code has a vulnerable function:

```
void CWE476_NULL_Pointer_Dereference__binary_if_01_bad() {
    ...
    if ((p != NULL) & (p->intOne == 5)) { ...e... }
    ...
}
```

with a solution in the same file:

```
if ((p != NULL) && (p->intOne == 5)) { ...e... }
```

note that the only difference is the '&&' instead of '&'. The bug occurs due to '&' not short-circuiting the execution path once it is known that 'p == NULL', causing p->intOne to run and a 'NULL' pointer is dereferenced.

3.3.1 Clang AST (C/C++)

An AST is a syntactic, tree-based representation of the source code which has a few advantages over raw code: it is hierarchical; comments and all white spaces are removed; and the AST can be independent of variable names and code formatting.

This is the same example as above displayed as an AST, from 'clang'[clang] using the '-Xclang -ast-dump' flag. (Some output omitted).

```
IfStmt
|-BinaryOperator '&'
```

```

| |-ParenExpr
| | `'-BinaryOperator '!='
| |   |-DeclRefExpr (Var twoIntsStructPointer)
| |   `'-CStyleCastExpr 'void_*' <NullToPointer>
| |     `'-IntegerLiteral 'int' 0
| `'-ParenExpr
|   `'-BinaryOperator '=='
|_-----|_-MemberExpr_>intOne
|_-----|_ `'-DeclRefExpr_'twoIntsStruct *'__(Var_
|         twoIntsStructPointer)
|_-----`'-IntegerLiteral_'int'_5
`-...e...

```

Note that the safe code again only differs in the line of the AST where

```
`BinaryOperator '\&' ` $\rightarrow$ `BinaryOperator '\&\&'`
```

The AST can be tagged with extra information such as at which line(s) a bug occurs.

3.3.2 LLVM IR

IR is a low-level representation close to assembly code, providing a simplified representation of the data, preserving semantic information. The specific representation we have chosen is LLVM IR [lattner2002llvm], a virtual level assembly which is used as a middle end for any programming language. Therefore, carrying vulnerability analysis at this level offers the possibility of generalising across multiple languages.

To illustrate LLVM IR, the example above has been converted to LLVM IR using 'clang -O0 -S -emit-llvm FILENAME.c', the '-O0' was used so that the resulting IR is not optimised.

This output is one basic block:

```

%1 = alloca %struct._twoIntsStruct*, align 8
store %struct._twoIntsStruct* null, %struct._twoIntsStruct
    ** %1, align 8

```

```

%2 = load %struct._twoIntsStruct*, %struct._twoIntsStruct
    ** %1, align 8
%3 = icmp ne %struct._twoIntsStruct* %2, null
%4 = zext i1 %3 to i32
%5 = load %struct._twoIntsStruct*, %struct._twoIntsStruct
    ** %1, align 8
%6 = getelementptr inbounds %struct._twoIntsStruct,
%struct._twoIntsStruct* %5, i32 0, i32 0
%7 = load i32, i32* %6, align 4
%8 = icmp eq i32 %7, 5
%9 = zext i1 %8 to i32
%10 = and i32 %4, %9                                ; the & in
    the if statement
%11 = icmp ne i32 %10, 0
br i1 %11, label %12, label %13

```

Then the solution function, when compiled, was split over multiple basic blocks

```

%1 = alloca %struct._twoIntsStruct*, align 8
store %struct._twoIntsStruct* null, %struct._twoIntsStruct
    ** %1, align 8
%2 = load %struct._twoIntsStruct*, %struct._twoIntsStruct**
    %1, align 8
%3 = icmp ne %struct._twoIntsStruct* %2, null
br i1 %3, label %4, label %10

; <label>:4:                                ; preds =
    %0
%5 = load %struct._twoIntsStruct*, %struct._twoIntsStruct**
    %1, align 8
%6 = getelementptr inbounds %struct._twoIntsStruct, %struct
    ._twoIntsStruct* %5, i32 0, i32 0
%7 = load i32, i32* %6, align 4
%8 = icmp eq i32 %7, 5
br i1 %8, label %9, label %10

```

The AST representations have a single character difference between the vulnerable code and the safe code while the IR representations have different numbers of basic blocks with very different content. This implies there is value from using the semantic knowledge of the compiler along with the AST.

3.3.3 Static Analysis

Clang is a static analyser commonly used in vulnerability detection. The output of the analyzer could be added to the AST graph as extra features.

```
void test(int *p) {  
    if (p)  
        return;  
  
    int x = p[0]; // warn  
}
```

The warning would run from the 'if' line until the 'int x = p[0]', however, only the dereference 'p[0]' is causing the vulnerability, and not the assignment.

A problem with running a static analysis tool directly is that it tends to flag as potential bugs far more issues than actually exist in the code. The 'scan-build' tool reports the following possible issues:

```
Allocator sizeof operand mismatch  
Assigned value is garbage or undefined  
Bad free  
Dead assignment  
Dead initialization  
Dereference of null pointer  
Dereference of undefined pointer value  
Division by zero  
Double free
```

Free alloca()
Memory leak
Offset free
Out-of-bound array access
Potential buffer overflow in call to 'gets'
Potential insecure temporary file in call 'mktemp'
Result of operation is garbage or undefined
Return of address to stack-allocated memory
Stack address stored into global variable
Undefined allocation of 0 bytes (CERT MEM04-C; CWE-131)
Uninitialized argument value
Unix API
Use-after-free

Each of these can be used as potential features for use in a classification algorithm. For some of the possible code vulnerabilities, this works quite well: for example, for 'CWE476' (Stack-based buffer overflow) 256 potential errors are detected, with less than a 10% false positive rate. For others, the static analysis tool performs rather poorly. For 'CWE121' (null pointer dereference), 3,164 potential errors are detected, with nearly 60% false positives. This suggests that certain types of vulnerabilities are more successfully addressed by current static analysis tools, while others provide more opportunity for machine learning.

3.4 Limitations

3.4.1 Contextual variability

While the challenge is addressed to encompass examples scraped from online repositories, Juliet only consists of synthetic examples. We considered a representation of the input data adapted for machine learning algorithms, which could accommodate both cases: a pair of functions, consisting of 1- the vulnerable function, 2- the corrected function. This dataset could then be augmented by such pairs constructed from real source code, a solution we explain in more details in section Using real world examples.

However, this representation has some limitations. For instance, it cannot capture bugs caused by multiple lines of code split over many function calls. Let us consider the following example:

```
f_check(int* p) {  
  if (p) {  
    f_safe(p)  
  }  
}  
  
f_safe(int* p) {  
  ...*p...  
}
```

In this case, the only call to the function 'f_safe' is made from another function which sanitises the variable. Then, considering functions without context, it would be impossible to differentiate between a dereference with a check in another function and a bug.

The main issue with representing data as function without context, is that depending on the call side of a function a variable can take different values, which implies that the vulnerability will only arise when calling a function in a specific state from another specific function. A data representation which accounts for function context may aid indicating specific code vulnerabilities in a context.

Nevertheless, creating this database would still be useful as either these functions could be merged together later or the ML algorithm could be designed to find the references between different functions.

3.4.2 Labelling

The difference between good and bad code can be very subtle. For example, the good and bad code mentioned in the section "Data Representation" differ only by one character. The Abstract Syntax Tree for bad code is:

```

IfStmt
|-BinaryOperator '&'
| |-ParenExpr
| | `|-BinaryOperator '!='
| |   |-DeclRefExpr (Var twoIntsStructPointer)
| |   `|-CStyleCastExpr 'void_*' <NullToPointer>
| |     `|-IntegerLiteral 'int' 0
| `|-ParenExpr
|   `|-BinaryOperator '=='
|_ _ _ _ _ |-MemberExpr_ ->intOne
|_ _ _ _ _ |_ `|-DeclRefExpr_ 'twoIntsStruct *_'_ (Var_
|_ _ _ _ _ |_ twoIntsStructPointer)
|_ _ _ _ _ `|-IntegerLiteral_ 'int' _5

```

The good code differs only in the value of the node with name 'BinaryOperator' at the top. If we use only the node names, such as 'BinaryOperator', the processed data for good code will be the same as for bad code. Let us call those data points ('X', 'safe') and ('X', 'vulnerable'). The training data will have the same data point 'X' classified as safe and vulnerable, therefore we cannot tell them apart, no matter how accurate the classifier. Such cases will require additional fine-tuning.

4 Machine Learning Approaches

4.0.1 Baseline

We built two baseline models for comparative purposes. First, a static analysis tool was run on the code and scored on how successfully it tagged functions as containing a weakness or not. As described above (subsection data representation - section static analysis), the static analyser returned flags for 22 potential vulnerabilities in the code, indicating for each of them whether they were present or not. The second baseline was provided by creating a zero-order model which was run on 1-AST node names as input features and 2-AST node names combined with static analysis results as input features.

Overview of baseline model

A common approach to programming language processing is to treat the code as natural language. For instance, AST nodes could be treated as independent words. In machine learning, the simplest and most common representation for natural language, called bag-of-words model, counts each word occurrence, ignoring features such as word order, word type or sentence structure. Taking into account all possible AST node names, each function was represented as a vector indicating whether each node type occurred in that function (1) or not (0).

The feature vector was analysed using Support Vector Machines (SVMs), a common approach for classifying text data into categories. In this case, the text consisted of the functions AST node names, and the category classification was whether the function was vulnerable (exhibited CWE121 weakness) or safe. In principle, an SVM looks for a decision boundary that separates the two sets of data (vulnerable and safe functions) so that the distance between the boundary and any data point of any class is the greatest possible. We used the sklearn SVM implementation with default parameter settings.

In a second iteration, we added the static analysis results as input features to the feature vector. For each bug-type checked by the tool, the input was

whether the static analyser indicated that vulnerability was present (1) or not (0) in the function. Again, the input was classified using SVMs.

4.0.2 Results

Static analysis

The static analysis was evaluated on how many correct and incorrect functions it flagged as having *any* vulnerability or not. It performed poorly on identifying stack buffer overflow issues. Precision was less than 40% and sensitivity was 20%, which implies that out of all the functions the static analyser flagged as containing a bug, fewer than 40% contained the CWE121 weakness. Besides, the static analyser only flagged about 20% of the CWE121 incorrect functions.

It is worth noting that the static analysis tool performance varies according to the weakness tested for, and CWE121 might be a particularly challenging case. Furthermore, some of the functions in the CWE121 dataset contain other vulnerabilities which the static analyser might flag.

Word cloud and SVM analysis

We explored the word clouds resulting from the bag of words for the CWE121 weakness on vulnerable and safe functions respectively.

As we can see, the word clouds are quite similar for both the vulnerable functions and their corrected version.

Correspondingly, while the SVM classifier had a rather high precision, sensitivity was low. In other words, for functions that were classified as potentially vulnerable, the classifier was correct more than 80% of the time. However, less than 40% of the faulty functions were correctly identified.

As a second step, we added the static analysis output as input features into the SVM classifier. Given the low performance of the static analyser in identifying this particular vulnerability, this did not improve the results.

weakness assigned a label of 0 and safe functions assigned a label of 1. Because in Juliet many examples contain multiple solutions for each vulnerable function, the number of safe examples (674) was greater than the number of vulnerable ones (267), which put chance performance at 71.6% for this dataset.

Once the model was trained on a subset (80%) of the data, its performance was tested on the remaining held-out data. The performance on this held-out data can be compared to the chance performance on that particular held-out sample. A model of this form offers many choices for representation of the data, model architecture, training, and evaluation.

4.1.2 Representation of the input

The input to the model was a sequence of tokens representing the function body. Tokens were then mapped uniquely to consecutive integers over all of the examples.

For example, the snippet of LLVM IR:

```
%structCharVoid = alloca %struct._charVoid, align 8
%1 = getelementptr inbounds %struct._charVoid,
%struct._charvoid* %structCharVoid, i32, 00, i32 1
store i8* getelementptr inbounds ([32 x i8], [32 x i8]* @.
    str i32 0, i32 0),
i8** %1, align 8
```

was mapped to the sequence:

```
190, 5, 349, 735, 447, 527, 707, 190, 170, 388,
612, 694, ...
```

Care must be taken that tokens specific to vulnerable or safe functions (and that therefore could be used to straightforwardly distinguish the

training examples) were not included. There were a few examples where a function body contained a token such as 'goodG2B1' or similar and we did not use these as training input.

Once the functions are represented as a sequence of integers, there are two options for how they can be fed into the model. The first, and simplest, is one-hot encoding, which maps an integer to a vector that is equal in length to the number of unique symbols in the dataset. All values of the vector are zero, with the exception of the n th entry, where n is the integer to be represented. For this encoding, we had a vocabulary of 801 symbols, leading to an 801-dimensional input vector.

We considered an alternative way to feed in the sequence through an embedding. Each integer was mapped to a vector whose length was less than the number of unique symbols. The mapping between integers and embedding vectors was learned as part of training a skip-gram model. In a skip-gram model, the goal is to predict what symbols are likely to be near a given input symbol [5] [ALEX]. We trained this skip-gram model the full set of functions used for this model. Thus, the embedding should have captured information about the context and relationship between different symbols. Because this representation is lower-dimensional than the one-hot encoding and contains an indication of 'meaning' of the symbols, it may increase the accuracy of the model. We used a 100-dimension embedding.

4.1.3 Architecture options

The simplest LSTM contains a single layer. We tested a single layer LSTM containing 400 hidden units under two circumstances: when the functions were constrained to length 700, and length 1000. In our dataset, according to the tokenization we used, the average function length was just under 700 integers. For all models tested, the output

classifier was a softmax function, which can easily be extended from binary classification to multi-way classification (for example, if the code were to be classified as containing one out of many weaknesses). The softmax also outputs a value between 0 and 1 for each label, which can be used to estimate confidence in the label.

A simple addition to the single layer architecture is to include another set of hidden units for which the input sequence is in reverse [4]. The final activity of these two sets of hidden units was then concatenated and fed into the classifier. This reduced the need for the network to remember inputs from the beginning of the sequence, as they were passed in again at the end. We tested this bi-directional network using 400 hidden units (in cases where embeddings were used, there were only 100 hidden units) in each set and sequences of length 1000.

Finally, another option we considered was to stack LSTMs to create a multi-layer model. In this scenario, at each time point the activity of the hidden units is fed into another LSTM and the final state of the hidden units in the second layer is passed into the classifier. We tested a 2-layer LSTM with 400 nodes per layer.

In all cases, the network was trained with mini-batch size 30 and 200 epochs of the data.

4.1.4 Results

The test set used to evaluate performance had 180 functions in total, 50 of which contained the weakness, giving a chance level of performance for a model that assumed all code was safe of 72.2 percent.

Overall accuracy for models with the given architecture:

- Single layer, 1000 sequence length: 78.3
- Single layer, 700 sequence length: 81.1
- Two layer, 1000 sequence length: 80.5
- Single layer, 1000 sequence length, using word embeddings (100 hidden units): 77.2

Figure 3: Precision (blue) and sensitivity (green) for each model

- Single layer, bidirectional, 700 sequence length: 75.5
- Single layer, bidirectional, 1000 sequence length using embeddings (100 hidden units): 72.2

The precision and sensitivity for each model (in the same order) is given in the following figure. A model that assumes all functions are safe has sensitivity of 0 (as it never detects a weakness). A model that assumes all functions are vulnerable has precision of .28 (the proportion of vulnerable functions in the data) and sensitivity of 1.

4.1.5 Complications and future directions

Converting the IR representation required choices about what to consider as an individual symbol, thereby impacting the length of the functions as well as how much information they conveyed. For example, there are many common symbols that occur at the start and end of files that may be better represented as a single 'start' or 'stop' symbol. Besides, for a sequential model, it is useful that the number of unique symbols and the average function length are moderate, rather than being unwieldy. However, the IR representation ignored structural elements captured by the AST which may be of use. This representation could also be used for some of the simpler analyses done on the AST representation, such as bag-of-words. Training the embeddings also involved parameter choices, most notably the size of the embedding dimension.

We only used examples (vulnerable and safe from a single weakness (CWE121)). Extending this procedure to multiple weaknesses would increase the amount of the data, which could be useful. The fact that our simplest model showed the best overall accuracy suggests more complicated models may suffer from a lack of data. More data would also be useful for training the embeddings. The embeddings we used could be improved, however, evaluating their quality will require a deep understanding of how the symbols in the LLVM representation relate to each other. The model can also be easily extended to be a multi-way classifier, however the handling of multiple errors in one file would not be straightforward.

This dataset contains examples that span over multiple functions or files. For the purposes of this model, we restricted ourselves only to the examples that were contained within one function. How to incorporate such longer-term dependencies would need further analysis. Concatenating called functions with their caller may be a reasonable starting point.

Because many vulnerable examples were paired with multiple safe solutions, this dataset had an imbalance in the number of vulnerable and safe examples of around 3:1. Real world code is likely to be much more imbalanced, as most code does not contain a given weakness. Dealing with such an imbalance is difficult.

Real world code also likely contains functions that are much longer than those used here, making a sequential model like an RNN difficult to generalize. To deal with this and the imbalance problem, it may be useful to use unsupervised learning (such as a clustering algorithm) to identify subsets of code that appear capable of containing a given weakness, then running a binary classifier for that weakness.

Another way to deal with long-term dependencies is to use a more hierarchical structure. Tree LSTMs [10] in particular may be able to capture structure in code as they do in natural languages.

Finally, a model such as this that is trained end-to-end via gradient descent is designed necessarily to optimize a particular loss function. Here, that loss function was meant to increase overall accuracy by decreasing the cross entropy, moving the model output closer to the true

label on all examples. If certain types of performance in the model are more important than others (precision vs recall, etc), those goals could be incorporated into the loss function to nudge the model performance in that direction.

4.2 Tree-Structured Conditional Random Fields (CRF)

Tree-structured conditional random fields (CRF)[8, 2] have recently been successfully applied to rumour stance classifications in Twitter conversations.[14] The following describes some preliminary modelling ideas developed during the week, on applying tree-structured CRF to abstract syntax trees constructed from code. Due to time constraints, no proof-of-concept has implemented, so the suggestions should be considered tentative.

4.2.1 Description

Tree-structured CRFs are an extension of CRFs which are typically applied to sequential data. To illustrate how CRF are applied to sequential data (also called *chain*), we can consider the example of part-of-speech tagging (POS). In POS, the goal is to label words in a sentence by their word class (e.g. Noun, Verb, Adjective). For this, we want to use the information of the preceding word to label the current word to exploit the sequential nature of the input sentences. This is done by defining a set of *feature functions* f_1, \dots, f_n that take as input the sentence X , the position of the i th word, the label of the current word l_i and the label of the preceding word l_{i-1} . Each feature function $f_j(X, i, l_i, l_{i-1})$ outputs a real number. These are then weighted by weights w_j and the weighted sum is transformed to a probability (e.g. using a softmax function). The goal of the learning algorithm is to learn the weights w_j using a test set of human-labelled sentences.

In the POS example the underlying structure is a chain. We can describe each word in a sentence as a node and the conditional dependencies as links between adjacent words. Thus sequential CRFs are a particular example of a graphical model. They can also be thought of as a discriminative and more general version of a hidden Markov model

(HMM). Additionally, they can be thought of as performing logistic regression on sequential data.

The power of CRFs is that they can be extended to model arbitrary graph structures instead of just sequences. For example, generalized CRFs have been applied to classify rumour stances in Twitter conversations [14]. Twitter conversations are modelled as trees in which each node is a single tweet and the dependency links represent the structure of tweets as replies to previous tweets originating from a source tweet (root node in the tree). Then the feature functions model the dependencies between the labels of the tweets (in the rumour stance example these could be *Supporting*, *Denying*, *Querying* or *Comment*) taking into account the conditional dependencies in the tree structure.

For our problem, we want to apply CRFs on ASTs. So an input to the CRF could be a full AST and the prediction task is to label each node (corresponding to each branch in the AST) as either correct code or vulnerable code. This requires labelling the nodes in the ASTs in the test set beforehand.

4.2.2 Labelling nodes on the ASTs in the test set

To apply CRFs on ASTs, we need to tag each node of the AST with a label. In the simplest case, for a vulnerability represented by a single AST, we can use binary labelling and, for each node i , assign a label $l_i \in \{0, 1\}$ indicating either safe code (0) or vulnerable code (1) at node i . An illustration of such an architecture is show in figure 4.

4.2.3 Features of AST nodes

The AST consists of nodes (function declarations, function calls, logical constructs, etc.) and a lot of information (memory addresses, operators, etc.) which can be used for feature extraction. In the simplest case we can treat all this extra information as a string and perform word embedding. However, feature extraction is a large area of research in general and in the specific case of ASTs of source code has not been explored and is likely to yield different results if adopting features commonly used in NLP.

The feature set could be further augmented by considering the generated LLVM IR for each node of the AST. The AST could then be tagged with extra information such as the line(s) a bug occurs. In section 3.3.2 we notice LLVM IR can provide semantic insight into the meaning of the AST.

4.2.4 Set-up

We recommend using PyStruct [6], a Python library for structured learning that implements CRF methods on general graph structures. This has the advantage over many other CRF packages that typically only implement sequential (chain) CRFs.

4.2.5 Examples of programs as CRF Trees

If we have a language with:

$$S ::= S; S | EE ::= x := E | NULL | n | \textit{if } E \textit{ then } E \textit{ else } E | * x | n, \dots, n$$

Where n is a number and x in a variable, then p will be a predicate. Then programs could then be mapped to CRF Trees, by first moving from a statement as a tree with many children to a list of statements in order.

```
(STMT  
(s1)  
(s2)  
(s3))
```

```
(STMT s1  
(STMT  
s2  
(STMT  
s3)))
```

This is an example.

Figure 4: AST-based CRF

```
x := NULL;
if(p) then *x else e2
```

The AST based CRF (see figure 4) will be initialised to be a complete tree with max depth and width calculated from the training set. When inferring labels over smaller ASTs than that of the model we can pad the observed AST with a padding node which will be ignored by the model.

For example, the minimal AST would be padded with symbol 'p' for max depth of 2 and max width of 1.

It may be possible to use start and stop characters instead of having to pad. However this is not as simple as in the case of linear chain CRFs since we are dealing with trees.

The AST-Tree CRF has a likelihood of the form (for a single AST):

$$P(\mathcal{T}_y|\mathcal{T}_{AST}) = \frac{1}{Z} \prod_{v \in Nodes} \exp \left\{ \sum w_j f_j (\mathcal{T}_{AST}, v, y_v, y_{parent(v)}) \right\}$$

Where \mathcal{T}_y represents the padded AST with ground truth labels as its nodes (y_v) and \mathcal{T}_{AST} represents the AST being evaluated.

The optimal labeling setting for a fixed set of parameters w_j and a given AST can be inferred with the max product algorithm using a similar routine to Viterbi. This is the prediction routine for the model. The model is trained over a training set by minimizing the negative log likelihood over the training set. A numerical optimisation routine can be used in order to update the parameters w_j . We use maxproduct to predict the labelings for every AST in the training data and we use these predictions to optimise the model.

Position independence Bugs of the same shape can appear anywhere in a program, approach above however would be sensitive to the positions of bugs in the training examples provide.

An extension could be to augment the training set by *convolving* each training example. This means take the root node of the function we are training with and place it over inference tree. Then at any point where the root node can be placed on the tree, create a full graph of padding with this tree. For example with example above we would get for the simple graph generated from 'x=1;*x' would create six new AST with the pair of nodes in every possible orientation. Some of the possible output graph are enumerated:

(x={1} (x[1] <p> <p>) (<p> <p> <p>))

(<p> (<p> <p> <p>) (x={1} x[1] <p>))
 (<p> (<p> <p> <p>) (x={1} <p> x[1]))

Then either all of these could be used as new training examples or a random subset.

5 Future work and research avenues

5.1 Using real-world examples

5.1.1 Overview

Although the Juliet Test Suite provides a clean basis to build a working model, real-life source code presents further difficulties, among which are:

- How to efficiently represent a large project?
- How to locate a safe line of code in a commit history and identify its relevant dependences?
- How to deal with refactoring / reformatting?

A promising avenue lies in collecting and analysing data from GitHub, which provides a profusion of current real-world examples of annotated code along with commit history and author information. This implies further challenges:

- Identifying relevant information (vulnerabilities, fixes, ...) in commits using natural language processing (NLP).
- Fitting the commit history behind a fix into a pair suited for the AST or finding an alternative representation

5.1.2 First steps towards augmenting the database

Using Github projects To augment the database of pairs of vulnerable and safe code samples that we used for classification, we need to build sets of pairs of functions corresponding to:

- The initial function that will capture the vulnerability. To this end, we need to identify when a vulnerability was effectively fixed.
- The final function where the vulnerability is fixed. This requires to be able to locate the relevant changes that contributed to fixing this

vulnerability through the complex history of branching, merging, reformatting, etc.

Proposed solution Rather than providing a full-fledged solution to integrate any project from Github to the existing database, we suggest building up from a small subset of reliably identifiable cases using existing literature [7, 3, 11] to single out the corrected revision of a designated vulnerability.

Building a reliable test set The main problem with examples taken from Github is that the correction will often involve several revisions, which may also include irrelevant modifications. However, by selecting a specific subset of the results returned by the previous algorithm, it should be possible to reliably supplement the database. We propose the following screening method:

- Safe function:
 - Restrict the results to the commits addressing a single issue, that was not mentioned previously in the revision history, and neither in the following history.
 - Select the whole blocks (functions or methods) where the fixes appear.
- Vulnerable function:
 - Restrict the results to the commit that directly precede the commit where the fix appears.

A Glossary

B.

1. Programming Language Processing

- CWE - common weakness enumeration
- IR - intermediate representation
- AST - abstract syntax tree

2. Machine Learning

- CNN - convolutional neural network
- RNN - recurrent neural network
- LSTM - long short term memory network (type of RNN)
- NLP - natural language processing
- CRF - conditional random field

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Team members

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Janis Klaise. Janis is completing a PhD in Mathematics and Complexity Science at the University of Warwick. His interests include applied network science and machine learning. For this project he looked into applying tree-structured conditional random fields to abstract syntax tree representations of the code.

Grace Lindsay: Grace recently completed her PhD in computational neuroscience at the Center for Theoretical Neuroscience at Columbia University. Her work focused on how neural changes associated with attention lead to enhanced performance on visual tasks. For this team, she worked on training RNN models to look for weaknesses in code snippets.

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